

A Facile Three-Steps, One-Pot Synthesis of Novel 2-Alkylamino and 2-Dialkylamino-4H-Pyrido [1, 2-A][1,3,5] Triazin-4-Ones from 2-Aminopyridine and 2-Aminopicolines

Said Dagdag^{1,2}, Mounir Belbahloul^{3,4}, Mohamed Anouar⁵, Maria Kopp², Abdellah Anouar³,
Mohamed Hmyene⁶

¹ University Hassan first. Settat, Morocco. Laboratory of Environmental and Development Sciences. Ecological chemistry team, Faculty of Science and Technology.

² Normandy Center for Studies and Research on Medicines, Faculty of Pharmaceutical Sciences, University of Caen. 5, rue Vaubénard, 14032 Caen Cedex, France.

³ University Hassan first. Settat, Morocco. Applied Chemistry and Environment Laboratory, Faculty of Science and Technology.

⁴ University Hassan first.. Settat, Morocco. Health Sciences and Technology Laboratory, higher institute of health sciences.

⁵ University Hassan first. Settat, Morocco. physico-chemistry of processes and materials Laboratory, Faculty of Science and Technology.

⁶ University Hassan first. Settat, Morocco. Matter and Instrumentation Radiation Laboratory, Faculty of Science and Technology.

ABSTRACT: A straightforward approach to novel 2-dialkylamino-4H-pyrido[1,2-a][1,3,5]triazin-4-ones synthesis is presented. The construction of these compounds was achieved by one-pot synthesis involving condensation of 2-aminopyridine or 2-aminopicolines with ethoxycarbonylthio cyanate, followed by amination of the thioureas, and finally thermal ring closure of resulting guanidines. This allowed access to the unreported title heterocycles. We described an efficient, facile, one-pot synthesis of a novel 2-dialkylamino-4H-pyrido[1,2-a][1,3,5]triazin-4-ones in order to obtain a library of pyridotriazines which will be used as building blocks in medicinal chemistry.

KEYWORDS: Heterocycles, Infrared and Masse Spectroscopy, NMR spectroscopy, pyridotriazines, Synthesis.

1. INTRODUCTION

The dialkylamino-4H-pyrido[1,2-a][1,3,5]triazin-4-ones skeleton is common in the structure of many natural and synthetic products associated with a broad spectrum of biological activities and pharmaceutical properties[1, 2]. In contrast with 2-dialkylamino-4H-pyrido[1,2-a][1,3,5]triazin-4-ones, which have extensively been used as building blocks in medicinal chemistry, few studies have addressed their analogues. To our knowledge, no reports have appeared concerning the synthesis of pyrido[1,2-a][1,3,5] triazin-4-ones skeleton 4_{a-e} (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Target molecules 4_{a-e} 2-dialkylamino-4H-pyrido[1,2-a][1,3,5]triazin-4-ones

It is interesting to find a facile and efficient methodology to synthesize this hitherto unknown annulated pyridine ring system. The relevance of pyrido[1,2-a][1,3,5]triazin-4-ones system arises from its wide biological activity, which stems from its antagonistic effect upon 5-HT₂ and 5-HT_{2a} serotonin receptors. Such effect can result in: mediating coronary blood flow[1], decreasing mean arterial blood pressure [3] and the antithrombotic effect in mammals [4]. Pyrido[1,2-a][1,3,5]triazine derivatives properties can be

used for prophylactic effect [2] or therapeutic treatment of other disorders such as: airway constriction in human or animals: asthma, emphysema, chronic bronchitis, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease [5], as well as various psychotic conditions including schizophrenia, depression, anorectic or bulimic eating disorders, and anxiety in humans [5]. Thymidine phosphorylase (TP) has been implicated in path physiological angiogenesis, anti-apoptosis and tumor growth [6,7]. The pyrido[1,2-a][1,3,5]triazines analogues, as potential TP inhibitors.

Oda *et al.* [7], described the syntheses of oligomers containing the new artificial C-deoxyribo nucleosides bearing pyrido[1,2-a][1,3,5]triazin-4-one derivatives. Some of C-deoxyribo nucleosides were able to convert to phosphoramidite reagents, which can be used for DNA synthesizers. In addition, the co-planarity and linearity [8,9] of this heterocyclic system could favor DNA intercalation and potentially provide anticancer compounds.

Demeunynck *et al.* [10] published a synthetic route to the 2-alkylaminoquinolino[2,3-f]quinazolin-1-one skeleton from 3-aminoacridine. The authors followed Manimala and Anslyn's methodology [11] by condensing the aminoacridines with ethoxycarbonylisothiocyanate followed by coupling with aliphatic amines and deprotection of the N-protected guanidine intermediates 5. That was ideally positioned to react by intramolecular Friedel-Crafts type substitution to form, in one step the fused pyrimidinone ring 6 (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Formation of quinazolino[2,3-f]quinazolin-1-one skeleton 6 from 3-aminoacridine

Reagents and conditions:

i) EtOOCNCS, DMF, rt. ii) Et₃N, RNH₂, EDCI(1-ethyl-3-(3-dimethylaminopropyl)carbodiimide), DMF, rt.

The same paper [10] also described a two-step methodology for substituted 2-propylamino quinazolin-4(3H)-ones from simple aromatic or heteroaromatic amines (Figure 3). The preparation of ethoxycarbonylguanidines was performed in one pot by careful control of the stoichiometry of the reagents successively added to the chosen aromatic amine dissolved in CH₂Cl₂. In most cases, the resulting protected guanidines were easily isolated with excellent levels of purity by simple precipitation from water.

Figure 3: Preparation of 2-propylaminoquinazolin-4(3H)-one 9

Reagents and conditions:

i) EtOOCNCS 1,2 equiv, CH₂Cl₂, rt, 90min, then Et₃N 3 equiv, PrNH₂ 2 equiv and EDCI 1,2 equiv, 6h, rt.

ii) ClSiMe₃ 5 or 10 equiv, DMF, 80°C.

On the other hand, we ourselves published [14] in 2002 a quasi-one-pot synthesis of 2-amino-4*H*-pyrido[1,2-*a*][1,3,5]triazin-4-ones from 2-aminopyridine (Figure 4). The isolation of the intermediates was not necessary and this sequence became applicable to parallel chemistry techniques.

Figure 4: Synthesis of 2-dialkylamino-4*H*-pyrido[1,2-*a*][1,3,5]triazin-4-ones (*4_{a-e}*) from 2-aminopyridines (*1_{a-e}*).

i) SCN-CO₂Et, DMF, rt, 2h ii) HNRR', HgCl₂, DMF, 0 - 5°C then rt, 4h iii) quasi one-pot: HCl, dioxane. iii) one-pot: DMF, 80°C, 2h

Primas *et al.* [12] have recently studied one pot syntheses of pyrimidocarbazole starting from 3-aminocarbazoles. In another paper, the same authors [13] described a three-steps methodology, one pot synthesis of novel 2-alkyl(aryl)amino and 2-dialkylamino-7*H*-[1,3,5]triazino[3,4-*b*]pyridoindol-4-one and derivatives starting 3-amino-β-carbolines in similar conditions to our work [14]. Finally, this project aims at synthesizing series of pyrido[1, 2-*a*][1,3,5]triazines analogues [14], *via* ring annulations, as potential TP inhibitors. In the following, we will report a new simple and efficient one-pot synthesis of hitherto unknown title compounds.

2. EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

Commercial reagents were purchased from Aldrich. Acros Organics and used as received without additional purification. Melting points were determined on a Kofler melting point apparatus and are uncorrected. Elemental analyses were performed at the "Institut de Recherche en Chimie Organique Fine" (Rouen, France) and they were found to be within ± 0.4% of theoretical values. IR spectra were taken with a Genesis Series FTIR spectrometer. Mass spectra were taken on JEOL. JMS GCM at spectrometer at the ionizing potential of 70 eV (EI) or were performed using a LC-MS Waters Alliance 2695 (ESI+) spectrometer. ¹HNMR (400 MHz) and ¹³CMR (100 MHz) spectra were recorded on a JEOL Lambda 400 spectrometer. Chemical shifts are expressed in parts per million downfield from tetramethylsilane as an internal standard. The organic extract was dried over MgSO₄ and evaporated under reduced pressure. Thin layer chromatography (TLC) was performed on silica gel 60F-264 (Merck). The filtration was carried out using celite 545 (Prolabo). 2-amino-5-iodo was prepared as reported in the literature [15].

General procedure for synthesis of 2-dialkylamino-4*H*-pyrido[1,2-*a*][1,3,5]triazin-4-ones using HgCl₂ (*1_{a-e}*)

A mixture of 2-aminopyridine *1_{a-e}* (0.02 mol) and ethoxycarbonylthiocyanate (0.02 mol) in anhydrous DMF (100 ml) was stirred at rt. for 2 hours to form the N-ethoxycarbonyl-N'-(pyridine-2-yl) thiourea intermediate *2_{a-e}*. The reaction mixture was then

cooled ($0 \pm 5^\circ\text{C}$) before saturation with the appropriate secondary amine (0.05 mol if the amine is not a gas) and the addition of mercuric chloride HgCl_2 (0.02 mol) was added successively under stirring. The temperature was allowed to reach rt. and stirring was continued at this temperature overnight. The reaction mixture was then heated under reflux for 2 hours; the black color which appeared was due to the formation of mercuric sulfide HgS , filtered through a celite pad. The filtrate was concentrated under reduced pressure and the solid precipitate was triturated with recrystallized solvent, filtered, dried, and then recrystallized from a large volume of solvent.

2-Amino-4H-pyrido[1,2-a][1,3,5]triazin-4-one (4a₁)

Recrystallization of the crude product from acetonitrile gave 4a_{1a} a white powder (1.55 g, 48 %), mp $> 260^\circ\text{C}$; IR(KBr): ν 3287, 3119, 1713, 1630 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6): 8.60 (d, J = 6.84 Hz, 1H), 7.86 (dd, J = 8.92 Hz, J = 6.68 Hz, 1H), 7.24 (s, 2H), 7.12 (d, J = 8.92 Hz, 1H), 7.00 (dd, J = 6.84 Hz, J = 6.68 Hz, 1H), ^{13}C N, 78.7. Anal. Calcd for $\text{C}_7\text{H}_6\text{N}_4\text{O}$ [M^+] 162, found: [MH^+] 162. Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_7\text{H}_6\text{N}_4\text{O}$: C: 51.85, H: 3.73, N: 34.55, Found: C: 51.56, H: 3.55, N: 34.62.

2-Dimethylamino-4H-pyrido[1,2-a][1,3,5]triazin-4-one (4a₂)

Recrystallization of the crude product from ether gave 4a_{2a} yellow powder (1.94 g, 51 %), mp 135°C ; IR (KBr): ν 3085, 1715, 1637 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6): 8.59 - 8.58 (d, J = 6.84 Hz, 1H), 7.87-7.83 (t, J = 8.16 Hz, J = 7.44 Hz, 1H), 7.10 (d, J = 8.88 Hz, 1H), 6.94 (m, 1H), 3.09 (s, 3H), 3.03 (s, 3H); ^{13}C NMR(DMSO- d_6): 161.6, 154.8, 149.9, 141.5, 129.3, 122.8, 113.9, 36.5, 36.3; MS, m/z = 190 (M^+), 175, 161, 146, 119, 78, 67. Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_4\text{O}$: C: 56.83; H: 5.83, N: 29.46, Found: C: 56.78, H: 5.34, N: 29.61.

2-Diethylamino-4H-pyrido[1,2-a][1,3,5]triazin-4-one (4a₃)

Recrystallization of the crude product from acetonitrile gave 4a_{3a} a white powder (1.66 g, 38 %), mp 176°C ; IR (KBr): ν 2974, 1683, 1633 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6): 8.59 (d, J = 6.84 Hz, 1H), 6.99 (m, 1H), 3.60 (q, J = 6.96 Hz, 2H), 3.53 (q, J = 6.84 Hz, 2H), 1.12 (t, J = 6.96 Hz, 3H), 1.11 (t, J = 6.84 Hz, 3H), ^{13}C NMR (DMSO- d_6): 160.6, 155.0, 149.9, 141.3, 129.3, 122.8, 113.7, 41.2, 41.0, 13.4, 12.9; MS, m/z = 218 (M^+), 203, 189, 146, 120, 78.7. Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_4\text{O}$: C: 60.53, H: 6.47, N: 25.67, Found: C: 60.68, H: 6.32, N: 25.56.

2-Dipropylamino-4H-pyrido[1,2-a][1,3,5]triazin-4-one (4a₄)

Recrystallization of the crude product from petroleum ether gave 4a_{4a} a yellow powder (1.92 g, 39 %), mp 90°C ; IR (KBr): ν 2962, 1710, 1631 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6): 8.58 (d, J = 6.96 Hz, 1H), 7.83 (dd, J = 8.88 Hz, J = 6.76 Hz, 1H), 7.14 (d, J = 8.88 Hz, 1H), 6.98 (m, 1H), 3.50 (m, 2H), 3.44 (m, 2H), 1.56 (m, 4H), 0.84 (t, J = 7.00 Hz, 6H); ^{13}C NMR (DMSO- d_6): 161.2, 154.8, 149.8, 141.3, 129.2, 122.8, 113.7, 48.5, 48.3, 20.9, 20.4, 11.2, 10.9; MS, m/z = 246 (M^+), 231.1, 175.1, 146.1, 120.1, 78.5. Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_4\text{O}$: C: 63.39; H: 7.37, N: 22.75, Found: C: 63.16, H: 7.41, N: 22.65.

2-Isopropylamino-4H-pyrido[1,2-a][1,3,5]triazin-4-one (4a₅) Recrystallization of the crude product from ether gave 4a_{5a} a white powder (0.60 g, 15 %), mp 139°C ; IR (KBr): ν 3212, 1720, 1595 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6): 8.55 (d, J = 6.72 Hz, 1H), 7.83 (dd, J = 8.80 Hz, J = 6.76 Hz, 1H), 7.66 (d, J = 7.20 Hz, 1H), 7.20 (d, J = 8.80 Hz, 1H), 6.93 (m, 1H), 4.12 (m, 1H), 1.13 (d, J = 5.72 Hz, 6H); ^{13}C NMR (DMSO- d_6): 160.8, 155.0, 149.8, 141.4, 129.2, 122.7, 113.8, 44.3, 22.5; MS, m/z = 204.2 (M^+), 189.2, 146, 119.4, 78.4, 45.8. Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_4\text{O}$: C: 58.81, H: 5.92, N: 27.43, Found: C: 58.92, H: 5.86, N: 27.34.

2-Cyclohexylamino-4H-pyrido[1,2-a][1,3,5]triazin-4-one (4a₆)

Recrystallization of the crude product from acetonitrile gave 4a_{6a} a grey powder (1.05 g, 21 %), mp 180°C ; IR (KBr): ν 3211, 2925, 1717, 1595; ^1H NMR(DMSO- d_6): 8.55 (d, J = 6.84 Hz, 1H), 7.80 (dd, J = 8.28 Hz, J = 6.84 Hz, 1H), 7.03 (d, J = 8.28 Hz, 1H), 6.93 (m, 1H), 3.73 (m, 1H), 3.35 (br, 1H), 1.80 (m, 2H), 1.68 (m, 2H), 1.56 (m, 1H), 1.24 (m, 4H), 1.08 (m, 1H); ^{13}C NMR (DMSO- d_6): 161.8, 155.6, 150.3, 141.6, 129.5, 122.8, 113.8, 49.0, 32.4, 24.7; MS, m/z = 244.2 (M^+), 216.2, 187.1, 162.1, 120.1, 99.1, 94.1, 78.7. Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_4\text{O}$: C: 63.90, H: 6.60, N: 22.94, Found: C: 64.03, H: 6.42, N: 22.66.

2-amino-9-methyl-4H-pyrido[1,2-a][1,3,5]triazin-4-one (4b₁)

Recrystallization of the crude product from acetonitrile gave 4b_{1a} a white powder (1.40 g, 40 %), mp $> 260^\circ\text{C}$; IR (KBr): ν 3377, 3155, 1690, 1647 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR(DMSO- d_6): 2.27 (s, 3H), 6.91 (dd, J = 6.76 Hz, J = 6.56 Hz, 1H), 7.27 (s, 2H), 7.74 (d, J = 6.76 Hz, 1H), 8.50 (d, J = 6.56 Hz, 1H); ^{13}C NMR (DMSO- d_6): 164.2, 155.4, 150.5, 139.0, 130.7, 126.9, 112.5, 16.4; MS, m/z = 176.0 (M^+); 161.0; 150.0; 134.0; 108.0; 92; 81.6.

2-Propylamino-9-methyl-4H-pyrido[1,2-a][1,3,5]triazin-4-one (4b₂)

Recrystallization of the crude product from acetonitrile gave 4b_{2a} a white powder (2.22g, 51 %), mp 146°C ; IR (KBr): ν 3530, 3045, 1726, 1652 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6), temperature at 100°C : 0.90 (t, J = 7.27 Hz, 3H), 1.57 (m, 2H), 2.29 (s, 3H), 3.29 (m, 2H) 6.86

(m, 1H), 7.41 (m, 1H), 7.67(m, 1H), 8.48(m, 1H); ¹³CNMR (DMSO-d₆): 162.5, 154.6, 150.8, 145.1, 127.2, 124.8, 122.6, 42.6, 17.7, 12.1; MS, m/z = 218 (M⁺), 203, 189, 175.99, 159.98, 134, 92, 84.

2-Isopropylamino-9-methyl-4H-pyrido[1,2-a][1,3,5]triazin-4-one (4b₃)

Recrystallization of the crude product from acetonitrile gave 4b₃ a white powder (2.22g, 51 %), mp 196 °C; IR (KBr): ν 3225, 3086, 1716, 1645 cm⁻¹; ¹HNMR (DMSO-d₆), temperature at 100°C: 1.18 (d, J = 6.67 Hz, 6H), 2.29 (s, 3H), 4.16 (m, 1H), 6.86 (m, 1H), 7.25 (m, 1H), 8.49 (m, 1H); ¹³CNMR (DMSO-d₆): 161.75, 153.84, 150.12, 142.96, 122.62, 121.68, 121.75, 41.80, 23.10, 17.12; MS, m/z = 218 (M⁺), 203, 176, 160, 134, 108, 92, 84.

2-Cyclohexylamino-9-methyl-4H-pyrido[1,2-a][1,3,5]triazin-4-one (4b₄)

Recrystallization of the crude product from acetonitrile gave 4b₄ a white powder (3.01g, 70 %), mp 176 °C; IR (KBr): ν 3232, 3086, 1720, 1642 cm⁻¹; ¹HNMR (DMSO-d₆): 1.08 (m, 1H, H_c), 1.25 (m, 3H, 3 H_c), 1.50 at 1.80 (m, 6H, 2.24 (s, 3H, 4H_b, 2H_a), 2.24 (s, 3H), 3.76 (m, 1H), 6.85 (s, 1H), 7.67 (m, 1H, H_a), 7.67 (m, 1H), 7.71 (m, 1H), 8.45 (m, 1H); ¹³CNMR (DMSO-d₆): 161.84, 155.12, 152.92, 137.04, 115.20, 112.35, 106.95, 49.06, 32.10, 25.12, 22.95; MS, m/z = 258 (M⁺), 200, 176, 132, 98, 84.

2-Diethylamino-9-methyl-4H-pyrido[1,2-a][1,3,5]triazin-4-one (4b₅)

Recrystallization of the crude product from acetonitrile gave 4b₅ a white powder (1.84g, 40 %), mp 124 °C; IR (KBr): ν 3180, 3070, 1670, 1610 cm⁻¹; ¹HNMR (DMSO-d₆): 1.10 (m, 6H), 2.20(s, 3H), 3.52 (m, 2H), 3.57 (m, 2H), 6.84 (dd, J = 5.87 Hz, J = 6.95 Hz, 1H), 7.66 (d, J = 5.87 Hz, 1H), 8.43 (d, J = 6.95 Hz, 1H); ¹³CNMR (DMSO-d₆): 160.07, 154.25, 150.18, 138.87, 130.73, 126.81, 112.65, 41.62, 41.06, 16.46, 13.00, 12.91; MS, m/z = 232 (M⁺), 217, 203, 160, 134, 92.0.

2-Dipropylamino-9-methyl-4H-pyrido[1,2-a][1,3,5]triazin-4-one (4b₆)

Recrystallization of the crude product from acetonitrile gave 4b₆ a white powder (1.66g, 32 %), mp 112 °C; IR (KBr): ν 2970, 2930, 1720, 1650 cm⁻¹; ¹HNMR (DMSO-d₆): 0.84(m, 6H), 1.55(m, 4H), 2.21(s, 3H), 3.42(t, ³J = 15.30 Hz, 2H), 3.49(t, ³J = 15.30 Hz, 2H), 6.85(dd, J = 6.75 Hz, J = 6.87 Hz, 1H), 7.67(d, J = 6.75 Hz, 1H), 8.43(d, J = 6.87 Hz, 1H); ¹³CNMR (DMSO-d₆): 160.66, 154.20, 150.23, 138.96, 130.78, 126.86, 112.74, 48.98, 48.42, 20.82, 20.50, 16.45, 11.35, 11.15; MS, m/z = 260 (M⁺), 231, 188.9, 159.9, 133.9, 92, 86, 72.9.

2-Diisopropylamino-9-methyl-4H-pyrido[1,2-a][1,3,5]triazin-4-one (4b₇)

Recrystallization of the crude product from acetonitrile gave 4b₇ a white powder (1.61 g, 31 %), mp 112 °C; IR (KBr): ν 2974, 2925, 1705, 1645 cm⁻¹; ¹HNMR (DMSO-d₆): 1.18 (d, ³J = 6.31 Hz, 6H), 1.37 (d, ³J = 6.19 Hz, 6H), 2.26 (s, 3H), 4.08 (m, 1H), 4.79 (t, 1H), 6.84 (dd, J = 6.95 Hz, J = 6.83 Hz, 1H), 7.68 (d, J = 6.95 Hz, 1H), 8.43 (d, J = 6.83 Hz, 1H); ¹³CNMR (DMSO-d₆): 160.21, 153.82, 149.96, 138.83, 130.79, 126.79, 112.62, 45.65, 45.41, 20.47, 19.74, 16.94; MS, m/z = 260 (M⁺), 217, 134, 92, 84.3.

2-amino-8-methyl-4H-pyrido[1,2-a][1,3,5]triazin-4-one (4c₁)

Recrystallization of the crude product from acetonitrile gave 4c₁ a pink powder (2.21g, 63 %), mp > 260 °C; IR (KBr): ν 3378 - 3300, 3150, 1680, 1642 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (DMSO-d₆): 2.37 (s, 3H), 6.78(m, 2H), 6.86 (d, J = 7.20 Hz, 1H), 6.92 (s, 1H), 8.51 (d, J = 7.20 Hz, 1H); ¹³C NMR (DMSO-d₆): 164.3, 155.0, 152.6, 149.6, 128.0, 119.7, 115.5, 20.4; MS, m/z = 176.0 (M⁺), 161.0, 150.0, 134.0, 108.0, 92.

2-Propylamino-8-methyl-4H-pyrido[1,2-a][1,3,5]triazin-4-one (4c₂)

Recrystallization of the crude product from acetonitrile gave 4c₂ a white powder (1.31g, 30 %), mp 138 °C; IR (KBr): ν 3520, 3035, 1730, 1650 cm⁻¹; ¹HNMR (DMSO-d₆), temperature at 100 °C: 0.90 (t, J = 14.47 Hz, 3H), 1.56 (m, 2H), 2.36 (s, 3H), 2.28 (m, 2H), 6.82 (m, 1H), 6.91(s, 1H), 7.16 (m, 1H) 8.49 (m, 1H); ¹³CNMR (DMSO-d₆): 163.1, 155.2, 150.5, 144.7, 127.0, 125.2, 123.1, 42.2, 23.1, 17.5, 12.1; MS, m/z = 218 (M⁺), 203, 189, 176, 160, 134, 108, 92, 84.3.

2-Isopropylamino-8-methyl-4H-pyrido[1,2-a][1,3,5]triazin-4-one (4c₃)

Recrystallization of the crude product from acetonitrile gave 4c₃ a white powder (1.18g, 27 %), mp 212 °C; IR (KBr): ν 3230, 3090, 1712, 1644 cm⁻¹; ¹HNMR (DMSO-d₆), temperature at 100 °C: 1.17 (m, 6H), 2.36 (s, 3H), 4.14 (m, 1H), 6.81 (m, 1H), 6.90 (s, 1H) 7.00 (m, 1H), 8.49 (m, 1H); ¹³CNMR (DMSO-d₆): 162.20, 154.10, 150.30, 143.75, 127.30, 122.72, 121.82, 42.10, 22.30, 17.20; MS, m/z = 218 (M⁺), 203, 189, 176, 160, 134, 108, 92.

2-Diethylamino-8-methyl-4H-pyrido[1,2-a][1,3,5]triazin-4-one (4c₅)

Recrystallization of the crude product from acetonitrile gave 4c₅ a white powder (2.09g, 45 %), mp 124 °C; IR (KBr): ν 3180, 3069, 1667, 1603 cm⁻¹; ¹HNMR (DMSO-d₆): 1.15 (m, 6H), 2.33 (s, 3H), 3.53 (m, 4H), 6.85 (s, 1H), 7.02 (s, 1H), 8.48 (s, 1H); ¹³CNMR

(DMSO- d_6): 161.60, 155.00, 150.20, 128.30, 121.10, 113.00, 41.70, 41.10, 16.50, 13.05, 12.95; MS, m/z = 232 (M^+), 217, 203, 189, 160, 134, 108.9, 92, 81.6.

2-Dipropylamino-8-methyl-4H-pyrido[1,2-a][1,3,5]triazin-4-one (4c₆)

Recrystallization of the crude product from acetonitrile gave 4c₆ a white powder (2.25g, 43 %), mp 112 °C; IR (KBr): ν 2961, 2932, 1713, 1648 cm^{-1} ; ¹H NMR (DMSO- d_6): 0.85(t, ³J = 7.00 Hz, 6H), 1.56 (m, 4H), 2.33(s, 3H), 3.42 (t, ³J = 7.00 Hz, 2H), 3.50 (t, ³J = 7.00 Hz, 2H), 6.85(d, J = 6.68 Hz, 1H), 7.00 (s, 1H), 8.48 (d, J = 6.68 Hz, 1H); ¹³C NMR (DMSO- d_6): 161.4, 154.50, 149.90, 128.50, 120.70, 116.00, 48.50, 48.30, 20.90, 20.50, 11.20; MS, m/z = 260 (M^+), 231, 217, 189, 160, 134, 108, 92.

2-Diisopropylamino-8-methyl-4H-pyrido[1,2-a][1,3,5]triazin-4-one (4c₇)

Recrystallization of the crude product from acetonitrile gave 4c₇ a white powder (2.08g, 40 %), mp 112 °C; IR (KBr): ν 2963, 2930, 1707, 1652 cm^{-1} ; ¹H NMR (DMSO- d_6): 1.27 (m, 12H), 2.34 (s, 3H), 4.47 (m, 2H), 6.84 (d, J = 7.07 Hz, 1H), 6.99 (s, 1H), 8.47 (d, J = 7.07 Hz, 1H); ¹³C NMR (DMSO- d_6): 160.89, 153.81, 152.49, 149.07, 128.00, 120.40, 115.00, 45.40, 45.23, 20.47, 20.07; MS, m/z = 260 (M^+), 217, 133, 99, 92, 84.

2-amino-7-methyl-4H-pyrido[1,2-a][1,3,5]triazin-4-one (4d₁)

Recrystallization of the crude product from acetonitrile gave 4d₁ a white powder (2.29g, 65 %), mp > 260 °C; IR (KBr): ν 3266, 3092, 1719, 1671, 1644 cm^{-1} ; ¹H NMR (DMSO- d_6): 2.28(s, 3H), 6.81 (m, 2H), 7.07(d, J = 8.7 Hz, 1H), 7.74 (d, J = 8.7 Hz, 1H), 8.45 (s, 1H); ¹³C NMR (DMSO- d_6): 164.0, 154.2, 150.5, 149.8, 143.4, 126.2, 112.7, 121.6, 16.8; MS, m/z = 176.0 (M^+), 134.0, 92.

2-Propylamino-7-methyl-4H-pyrido[1,2-a][1,3,5]triazin-4-one (4d₂)

Recrystallization of the crude product from acetonitrile gave 4d₂ a white powder (2.40g, 65 %), mp 140 °C; IR (KBr): ν 3525, 3044-2963, 1728, 1649 cm^{-1} ; ¹H NMR (DMSO- d_6), temperature at 100 °C: 0.89 (m, 3H), 1.54 (m, 2H), 2.26 (s, 3H), 3.26 (m, 2H), 7.04 (m, 1H), 7.27(m, 1H), 7.70 (m, 1H), 8.42 (s, 1H); ¹³C NMR (DMSO- d_6): 162.7, 154.5, 150.6, 144.6, 126.8, 124.4, 122.4, 42.4, 22.6, 17.6, 11.7; MS, m/z = 218 (M^+), 189, 160, 134, 108, 92.

2-Isopropylamino-7-methyl-4H-pyrido[1,2-a][1,3,5]triazin-4-one (4d₃)

Recrystallization of the crude product from acetonitrile gave 4d₃ a white powder (2.40g, 55 %), mp 206 °C; IR (KBr): ν 3222, 3094 - 2968, 1714, 1649 cm^{-1} ; ¹H NMR (DMSO- d_6), temperature at 100 °C: 1.10 (d, J = 6.5 Hz, 6H), 2.26 (s, 3H), 4.15 (m, 1H), 7.05 (m, 1H), 7.12(m, 1H), 7.70 (m, 1H), 8.41(s, 1H); ¹³C NMR (DMSO- d_6): 161.50, 153.93, 149.58, 143.46, 126.27, 122.51, 121.67, 41.75, 22.19, 17.15; MS, m/z = 218 (M^+), 203, 176, 160, 134, 108, 92.

2-Cyclohexylamino-7-methyl-4H-pyrido[1,2-a][1,3,5]triazin-4-one (4d₄)

Recrystallization of the crude product from acetonitrile gave 4d₄ a beige sheet powder (1.81g, 35 %), mp = 260 °C; IR (KBr): ν 3224, 3094-2924, 1715, 1649 cm^{-1} ; ¹H NMR (DMSO- d_6): 1.30 (m, 5H), 1.60 at 1.86 (m, 6H), 2.26 (s, 3H), 3.18 (m, 1H), 7.15 (m, 1H), 7.71 (m, 1H), 8.41 (s, 1H); ¹³C NMR (DMSO- d_6): 161.92, 155.15, 153.75., 136.52, 114.87, 112.18, 107.15, 48.85, 31.95, 25.04, 23.75; MS, m/z = 258 (M^+), 224, 201, 176, 143, 133, 99.

2-Diethylamino-7-methyl-4H-pyrido[1,2-a][1,3,5]triazin-4-one (4d₅)

Recrystallization of the crude product from diethyl ether gave 4d₅ a white powder (3.06g, 66 %), mp 90 °C; IR (KBr): ν 2969, 2932, 1712, 1644 cm^{-1} ; ¹H NMR (DMSO- d_6): 1.09 (d, J = 4.47 Hz, 6H), 2.22 (s, 3H), 3.5 (q, ³J = 13.70 Hz, 2H), 3.56 (q, ³J = 13.70 Hz, 2H), 7.05 (d, J = 8.95 Hz, 1H), 7.68 (d, J = 8.95 Hz, 1H), 8.38 (s, 1H); ¹³C NMR (DMSO- d_6): 160.00, 153.75, 149.76, 143.63, 126.33, 123.07, 122.28, 41.09, 40.89, 13.33, 12.90; MS: m/z = 232 (M^+), 203, 189, 160, 134, 108, 92.

2-Dipropylamino-7-methyl-4H-pyrido[1,2-a][1,3,5]triazin-4-one (4d₆)

Recrystallization of the crude product from acetonitrile gave 4d₆ a white powder (2.70g, 52 %), mp 120 °C; IR (KBr): ν 3023, 2961, 1720, 1649 cm^{-1} ; ¹H NMR (DMSO- d_6): 0.85 (t, ³J = 13.27 Hz, 6H), 1.57 (m, 4H), 2.24(s, 3H), 3.43 (t, ³J = 14.26 Hz, 2H), 3.50 (t, ³J = 13.90 Hz, 2H), 7.10 (d, J = 8.95 Hz, 1H), 7.73 (d, j = 8.95 Hz, 1H), 8.42(s, 1H); ¹³C NMR (DMSO- d_6): 161.06, 153.70, 149.82, 143.76, 126.37, 123.17, 122.40, 48.48, 48.27, 20.44, 18.92, 17.18, 11.15, 10.96; MS, m/z = 260 (M^+), 217, 203, 160, 134, 92.

2-Diisopropylamino-7-methyl-4H-pyrido[1,2-a][1,3,5]triazin-4-one (4d₇)

Recrystallization of the crude product from acetonitrile gave 4d₇ a white powder (2.60g, 50 %), mp 210 °C; IR (KBr): ν 2970, 2930, 1710, 1650 cm^{-1} ; ¹H NMR (DMSO- d_6): 1.30 (d, J = 3.75 Hz, 12H), 2.25 (s, 3H), 4.45 (m, 2H), 7.10 (d, J = 8.59 Hz, 1H), 6.99 (s, 1H), 7.72 (d, J = 8.59 Hz, 1H), 8.41 (s, 1H); ¹³C NMR (DMSO- d_6): 160.68, 153.22, 149.45, 143.58, 126.24, 123.00, 122.41, 45.53, 45.40, 20.59, 20.02, 17.19; MS, m/z = 260 (M^+), 231, 217, 189, 160, 134, 92, 72.

2-Morpholino-7-methyl-4H-pyrido[1,2-a][1,3,5]triazin-4-one (4d₈)

Recrystallization of the crude product from acetonitrile gave 4d₈ a white powder (2.42g, 49 %), mp 208°C; IR (KBr): ν 3093 - 2945, 1702, 1646 cm⁻¹; ¹HNMR (DMSO-d₆): 2.26 (s, 3H), 3.61 (m, 4H), 3.77 (m, 4H), 7.15 (d, J = 8.51 Hz, 1H), 7.79 (d, J = 8.51 Hz, 1H), 8.45 (s, 1H); ¹³CNMR (DMSO-d₆): 160.69, 153.99, 149.00, 144.22, 126.64, 123.83, 122.33, 65.95, 43.76, 17.21; MS, m/z = 246 (M⁺), 231.

2-amino-6-methyl-4H-pyrido[1,2-a][1,3,5]triazin-4-one (4e₁)

Recrystallization of the crude product from acetonitrile gave 4e₁ a white powder (2.29g, 65 %), mp > 260 °C; IR (KBr): ν 3266, 3092, 1719, 1671, 1644 cm⁻¹; ¹HNMR (DMSO-d₆): 2.29 (s, 3H), 6.87 (dd, J = 6.65, J = 6.67 Hz, 1H), 7.27 (s, 2H), 7.74 (d, J = 6.65 Hz, 1H), 8.50 (d, J = 6.67 Hz, 1H); ¹³CNMR (DMSO-d₆): 164.2, 154.2, 150.5, 139.00, 130.75, 126.2, 112.50, 16.40; MS: m/z = 176.0 (M⁺); 161, 150, 134, 108, 92.

2-Diethylamino-6-methyl-4H-pyrido[1,2-a][1,3,5]triazin-4-one (4e₂)

Recrystallization of the crude product from diethylether gave 4e_{2a} a white powder (1.84g, 40 %), mp 122°C; IR (KBr): ν 3110 - 3070, 1690, 1640 cm⁻¹; ¹HNMR (DMSO-d₆): 1.11 (m, 6H), 2.26 (s, 3H), 3.53 (m, 2H), 3.58 (m, 2H), 6.43 (d, J = 8.15 Hz, 1H), 6.48 (d, J = 7.50 Hz, 1H), 7.32 (m, 1H); ¹³CNMR (DMSO-d₆): 160.13, 154.12, 150.23, 138.92, 130.70, 126.63, 112.59, 41.72, 41.32, 16.48, 13.03, 12.93; MS: m/z = 232 (M⁺), 217, 203, 160, 134, 92.

2-Dipropylamino-6-methyl-4H-pyrido[1,2-a][1,3,5]triazin-4-one (4e₃)

Recrystallization of the crude product from acetonitrile gave 4e_{3a} a white powder (2.15g, 41 %), mp 120°C; IR (KBr): ν 2961, 2930, 1699, 1614 cm⁻¹; ¹HNMR (DMSO-d₆): 0.84 (t, ³J = 13.27 Hz, 6H), 1.57 (m, 4H), 2.24 (s, 3H), 3.43 (t, ³J = 14.26 Hz, 2H), 3.50 (t, ³J = 13.90 Hz, 2H), 7.10 (d, J = 8.95 Hz, 1H), 7.73 (d, j = 8.95 Hz, 1H), 8.42 (s, 1H); ¹³CNMR (DMSO-d₆): 161.06, 153.70, 149.82, 143.76, 126.37, 123.17, 122.40, 48.48, 48.27, 20.44, 18.92, 17.18, 11.15, 10.96; MS: m/z = 260 (M⁺), 217, 203, 160, 134, 92.

2-Diisopropylamino-6-methyl-4H-pyrido[1,2-a][1,3,5]triazin-4-one (4e₄)

Recrystallization of the crude product from acetonitrile gave 4e_{4a} a white powder (2.16g, 42 %), mp 128°C; IR (KBr): ν 2960, 2930, 1700, 1614 cm⁻¹; ¹HNMR (DMSO-d₆): 1.19 (d, J = 6.54 Hz, 6H), 1.36 (d, J = 6.24 Hz, 6H), 2.27 (s, 3H), 4.07 (m, 1H), 4.80 (m, 1H), 6.41 (d, J = 8.10 Hz, 1H), 6.45 (d, J = 7.32 Hz, 1H), 7.30 (m, 1H); ¹³CNMR (DMSO-d₆): 160.22, 153.84, 150.07, 138.90, 130.95, 126.80, 112.65, 45.75, 45.43, 20.55, 19.95, 16.95; MS: m/z = 260 (M⁺), 217, 160, 134, 92.

Synthesis of 2-Pyrrolo-(7 or 8)-methyl-4H-pyrido[1,2-a][1,3,5]triazin-4-one 7_{a-b} :

2-amino-(7 or 8)-methyl-4H-pyrido[1,2-a][1,3,5]triazin-4-one (0.01 mol) is dissolved in acetic acid (50 ml), and 2,5-dimethoxytetrahydrofuran (0.01 mol) were added and then heated under reflux for 3 hours, the mixture was concentrated under reduced pressure and the solid precipitate was triturated with recrystallized solvent, filtered, dried and then recrystallized from a large volume of solvent.

Synthesis of 2-Alkoxy(7 or 8)-methyl-4H-pyrido[1,2-a][1,3,5]triazin-4-one 8_{a-h} :

2-amino-(7 or 8)-methyl-4H-pyrido[1,2-a][1,3,5]triazin-4-one (0.01 mol) is dissolved in acetic acid (50 ml), and alkyl anhydride (0.01 mol) were added and then heated under reflux for 2 hours, the mixture was concentrated under reduced pressure and the solid precipitate was triturated with recrystallized solvent filtered, dried and then recrystallized from a large volume of solvent.

2-Pyrrolo-7-methyl-4H-pyrido[1,2-a][1,3,5]triazin-4-one (7_a)

Recrystallization of the crude product from acetonitrile gave 7_a a white powder (1.40 g, 62 %), mp 208°C; IR (KBr): ν 3097-2963, 1722, 1641 cm⁻¹; ¹HNMR (DMSO-d₆): 2.40 (s, 3H), 6.33 (s, 2H), 7.58 (d, J = 8.87 Hz, 1H), 7.69 (s, 2H), 8.11 (d, J = 8.87 Hz, 1H), 8.78 (s, 1H); ¹³CNMR (DMSO-d₆): 157.22, 153.98, 150.03, 145.48, 127.69, 127.47, 123.09, 118.90, 112.17, 17.07; MS: m/z = 226 (M⁺), 160, 92.

2-Pyrrolo-8-methyl-4H-pyrido[1,2-a][1,3,5]triazin-4-one (7_b)

Recrystallization of the crude product from acetonitrile gave 7_b a white powder (1.35g, 60 %), mp 214°C; IR (KBr): ν 3100 - 2970, 1720, 1640 cm⁻¹; ¹HNMR (DMSO-d₆): 2.54 (s, 3H), 6.38 (s, 2H), 7.37 (m, 1H), 7.52 (s, 1H), 7.73 (s, 2H), 8.85 (m, 1H); ¹³CNMR (DMSO-d₆): 156.93, 15.20, 151.10, 145.50, 127.80, 127.50, 122.95, 119.12, 112.16, 17.20; MS: m/z = 226 (M⁺), 160, 92.

2-Acetoxyamino-7-methyl-4H-pyrido[1,2-a][1,3,5]triazin-4-one (8_a)

Recrystallization of the crude product from ethanol gave 8_a a white powder (1.44g, 66 %), mp 228°C; IR (KBr): ν 3249, 3026, 1712, 1690, 1644 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (DMSO-d₆): 2.26 (s, 3H), 2.37 (s, 3H), 2.24 (s, 3H), 7.42 (d, J = 8.87 Hz, 1H), 8.02 (d, J = 8.87 Hz, 1H),

8.68 (s, 1H), 10.44 (s, 1H); ^{13}C NMR (DMSO- d_6): 170.05, 154.13, 150.41, 146.70, 127.14, 123.99, 122.00, 25.37, 16.76; MS: m/z = 218 (M^+), 203, 175, 160, 133, 108, 92.

2-Propoxyamino-7-methyl-4H-pyrido[1,2-a][1,3,5]triazin-4-one (8_b)

Recrystallization of the crude product from ethanol gave 8_ba white powder (1.51g, 65 %), mp 186°C; IR (KBr): ν 3288, 3077, 1734, 1701, 1646 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6): 1.03 (t, 3J = 14.70 Hz, 3H) 2.37 (s, 3H), 2.58 (q, 3J = 14.70 Hz, 2H), 7.40 (d, J = 8.87 Hz, 1H), 8.02 (d, J = 8.87 Hz, 1H), 8.68 (s, 1H), 10.39 (s, 1H); ^{13}C NMR (DMSO- d_6): 173.33, 160.24, 154.17, 150.45, 145.22, 127.20, 127.05, 123.12, 30.24, 17.41, 8.87; MS: m/z = 232 (M^+), 203, 175, 160, 133, 92, 81.

2-Butoxyamino-7-methyl-4H-pyrido[1,2-a][1,3,5]triazin-4-one (8_c)

Recrystallization of the crude product from ethanol gave 8_ca white powder (1.52 g, 62%), mp 175°C; IR (KBr): ν 3274, 2954-2872, 1726, 1707, 1646 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6): 0.89 (m, 3H), 1.57 (m, 2H), 2.37 (s, 3H), 2.53 (m, 2H), 7.41 (d, J = 8.11 Hz, 1H), 8.02 (d, J = 8.11 Hz, 1H), 8.68 (s, 1H), 10.40 (s, 1H); ^{13}C NMR (DMSO- d_6): 172.31, 160.22, 154.17, 150.46, 145.21, 127.20, 127.06, 123.13, 17.93, 17.41, 13.56; MS: m/z = 246 (M^+), 231, 203, 175, 160, 133, 92.

2-Isobutoxyamino-7-methyl-4H-pyrido[1,2-a][1,3,5]triazin-4-one (8_d)

Recrystallization of the crude product from ethanol gave 8_da white powder (1.48 g, 60 %), mp 167°C; IR (KBr): ν 3317 - 3268, 3060 - 2926, 1715, 1691, 1646 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6): 1.05 (d, J = 6.67 Hz, 6H), 2.37 (s, 3H), 2.9 3(m, 1H), 7.40 (d, J = 9.15 Hz, 1H), 8.03(d, J = 9.15 Hz, 1H), 8.68 (s, 1H), 10.43 (s, 1H); ^{13}C NMR (DMSO- d_6): 173.80, 160.30, 156.10, 153.20, 148.30, 128.01, 126.75, 122.53, 51.10, 27.93, 20.55, 19.70; MS: m/z = 246 (M^+), 203, 175, 160, 134, 92, 81.6.

2-Hexyloxyamino-7-methyl-4H-pyrido[1,2-a][1,3,5]triazin-4-one (8_e)

Recrystallization of the crude product from isopropanol gave 8_ea white powder (1.64g, 60%), mp 167°C; IR (KBr): ν 3292 - 3077, 2951 - 2855, 1731, 1705, 1647 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6): 0.85 (m, 3H), 1.27 (m, 4H), 1.54 (m, 2H) 2.36 (s, 3H), 2.54 (m, 2H), 7.40 (d, J = 8.87 Hz, 1H), 8.03 (d, J = 8.87 Hz, 1H), 10.42 (s, 1H); ^{13}C NMR (DMSO- d_6): 172.44, 160.20, 154.16, 150.45, 145.21, 127.20, 127.04, 123.12, 38.75, 30.78, 24.18, 21.87, 17.40, 13.83; MS: m/z = 274 (M^+), 231, 203, 175, 160, 133, 108, 92.

2-Acetoxyamino-8-methyl-4H-pyrido[1,2-a][1,3,5]triazin-4-one (8_f)

Recrystallization of the crude product from ethanol gave 8_fa white powder (1.42g, 65%) mp 163°C; IR (KBr): ν 3250-3200, 3028-3010, 1710, 1690, 1640 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6): 2.30 (s, 3H), 2.52(s,3H), 7.25 (d, J = 6.95 Hz, 1H), 7.32 (s, 1H) 8.74 (d, J = 6.67 Hz, 1H), 10.45 (s, 1H); ^{13}C NMR (DMSO- d_6): 170.10, 160.70, 155.40, 155.00, 150.40, 129.00, 121.70, 119.20, 25.40, 21.10; MS: m/z = 218 (M^+), 203, 175, 160, 133, 108, 92.

2-Propoxyamino-8-methyl-4H-pyrido[1,2-a][1,3,5]triazin-4-one (8_g)

Recrystallization of the crude product from ethanol gave 8_ga white powder (1.39g, 60%), mp 172°C; IR (KBr): ν 3290, 3080-2990, 1730, 1705, 1642 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6): 1.05 (m, 3H), 2.51 (s, 3H), 2.62 (m, 2H), 7.24 (d, J = 5.60 Hz, 1H), 7.31 (s, 1H), 8.75 (d, J = 5.60 Hz, 1H), 10.43(s, 1H); ^{13}C NMR (DMSO- d_6): 173.38, 160.70, 155.33, 155.06, 150.51, 129.01, 121.71, 119.22, 30.26, 21.13, 8.95; MS: m/z = 232 (M^+), 203, 175, 160, 133, 92, 81.

2-Isobutoxyamino-8-methyl-4H-pyrido[1,2-a][1,3,5]triazin-4-one (8_h)

Recrystallization of the crude product from ethanol gave 8_ha white powder (1.47g, 60%), mp 169°C; IR (KBr): ν 3320 - 3270, 3060 - 2930, 1710, 1690, 1645 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6): 1.08 (m, 6H), 2.51 (s, 3H), 3.00 (m, 1H), 7.23(m, 1H), 7.30 (s,1H), 8.74 (m,1H) 10.43 (s, 1H); ^{13}C NMR (DMSO- d_6): 175.90, 160.82, 155.33, 155.12, 150.62, 128.06, 122.60, 116.72, 50.57, 28.64, 20.52, 19.71; MS: m/z = 246 (M^+), 203, 175, 160, 134, 92.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

As a first approach towards the synthesis of this heterocyclic system we envisaged a synthetic strategy using 2-aminopyridine or derivatives as starting material. Thus, a solution of the compound in anhydrous DMF was treated at the room temperature with ethoxycarbonyl isothiocyanate, and to the resulting thiourea, the appropriate dialkylamine and HgCl_2 were added to obtain the ethoxycarbonylguanidines. Heating the DMF solution of the latter compounds under reflux induced a ring closure of the ethoxycarbonyl function into a triazine ring and the products obtained were identified as 2-dialkylamino-4H-pyrido [1,2-a][1,3,5]triazin-4-ones.

Furthermore, considering that no work has yet taken advantage of these new methods yet to produce cyclic polysubstituted guanidines by direct ring closure of suitable substrates, we studied the total one pot synthesis of 2-dialkylamino-4H-pyrido[1,2-

a][1,3,5]triazin-4-ones starting 2-aminopyridines and 2-aminopicolines 1_{a-h}. We would now like to report a new simple and efficient one-pot synthesis of the hitherto unknown compounds.

In the light of all these works, we first verified a general method for the one pot syntheses 2-dialkylamino-4*H*-pyrido[1,2-*a*][1,3,5]triazin-4-ones starting 2-aminopyridines 1_{a-e} usable in combinatorial approaches.

In order to build blocks, we focused on a general protocol facile three-steps, for the synthesis 2-dialkylamino-4*H*-substituted-pyrido[1,2-*a*][1,3,5]triazin-4-ones skeleton 4_{a-e} starting 2-amino pyridine 1_a; 2-aminopicolines 1_{b-e}. With this aim, we particularly studied the synthesis of compounds skeleton 4_{a-e} according to the (Figure 3). We envisaged a synthetic strategy using 2-aminopyridines 1_{a-e} as starting material. Thus, a solution of 2-aminopyridine in anhydrous DMF was treated at room temperature with ethoxy carbonylthiocyanate, and to the resulting *N*-ethoxycarbonyl-*N'*-(2-pyridyl)thiourea 2_{a-e} intermediate which was next able to produce by reaction with appropriate dialkylamines in mercuric chloride to obtain the ethoxycarbonylguanidines 3_{a-e}. Heating the DMF solution of the latter compounds under reflux induced a ring closure of the ethoxycarbonyl function into a triazine ring and the products obtained as 2-dialkylamino-4*H*-pyrido[1,2-*a*][1,3,5]triazin-4-ones 4_{a-e} in good yield through a one-pot protocol starting 2-aminopyridine 1_a and 2-aminopicolines 1_{b-e} (Figure 4). The isolation of the two intermediates 2_{a-e} and 3_{a-e} was an unnecessary sequence that became applicable to parallel chemistry techniques.

Figure 5: Synthesis of 2-pyrrolo-4*H*-pyrido[1,2-*a*][1,3,5]triazin-4-ones (7_{c-d}) and amides corresponding (8_{a-h}) derivatives from 2-amino-4*H*-pyrido[1,2-*a*][1,3,5]triazin-4-ones (4_{c-d}).

Reagents and conditions:

i) 2,5-dimethoxytetrahydrofuran, acetic acid, 90°C, 3h. ii) alkyl anhydride, acetic acid, 90°C, 2h.

We studied the synthesis of 2-pyrrolo-4*H*-Pyrido[1,2-*a*][1,3,5]triazin-4-ones 7_{c-d} following Clausson-Kass's methodology [16] by condensing in acetic acid and heating for 3 hours, the 2-amino-4*H*-pyrido[1,2-*a*][1,3,5]triazin-4-ones 4_{a-b} with 2,5-dimethoxytetrahydrofuran to give 8_{a-b} in good yields. 2-amino-4*H*-pyrido[1,2-*a*][1,3,5]triazin-4-ones 4_{c-d} react with many anhydride acids, in acetic acid mild condition, by heating and give the corresponding amides 8_{a-h} (Figure 5). We also attempted to apply the HgCl₂ methodology to primary or secondary amines (aliphatic or aromatic), but this was unsuccessful and no cyclized products were being observed [14,16]. This failure prompts us to modify our reaction conditions.

4. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, we have developed facile and efficient three-steps, synthesis system of novel class of hetero-aromatic compounds, namely:

2-dialkylammino-4*H*-pyrido [1, 2-*a*][1, 3, 5] triazin-4-ones starting 2-aminopyridine_{1a} or 2-aminopiccolines_{1b-e}

The success of this protocol as one-pot synthesis of compounds of the title further underscores the ease as well as the efficiency of this protocol. The co-planarity and linearity of this heterocyclic scaffold suggest that the 2-amino derivatives may intercalate between DNA base pairs. Further biological studies are in progress. Additional experiments concerning the synthesis of 2-diethylammino-7-(Het)aryl-4*H*-pyrido [1,2-*a*][1,3,5]triazin-4-ones skeleton type 4 using palladium catalyzed Suzuki type coupling, are currently under investigation in order to obtain great potentialities in medicinal chemistry of compounds class.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors would like to thank Professor Sylvain Rault, director of C.E.R.M.N. and Jean Charles Lancelot engineer of research, for their financial support and their fruitful insights. The authors would also like to thank the referees for their suggestions and comments which have tremendously improved the manuscript.

REFERENCES

1. T. Tanaka, Y. Morishima, K. Watanabe, T. Shibutani, M. Yasuoka, and T. Shibano, "Combined effect of the 5-HT₂ receptor antagonist DV-7028 and aspirin or heparin on coronary cyclic flow reductions in dogs," *Cardiovascular Research*, vol. 27, pp. 1374-1379, 1993.
2. B. Zaleska, B. Trzewik, E. Stodolak, J. Grochowski, and P. Serda, "One-Pot Synthesis of 3, 4-Dihydro-2*H*-pyrido [1, 2-*a*][1, 3, 5] triazin-2-one Derivatives from N-(2'-Pyridinyl) benzoylacetamide and Nitrosobenzenes," *Synthesis*, vol. 2004, pp. 2975-2979, 2004.
3. D. Pawlak, M. Adamkiewicz, J. Malyszko, A. Takada, M. Mysliwiec, and W. Buczko, "Vascular and cardiac effects of DV-7028, a selective, 5-HT₂-receptor antagonist in rats," *Journal of Cardiovascular Pharmacology*, vol. 32, pp. 266-273, 1998.
4. T. Shibano, T. Tanaka, Y. Morishima, M. Yasuoka, K. Watanabe, and F. Fujii, "Pharmacological profile of a new 5-hydroxytryptamine₂ receptor antagonist, DV-7028," *Archives Internationales de Pharmacodynamie et de Therapie*, vol. 319, pp. 114-128, 1992.
5. S. Sengupta, L. A. Sellers, H. B. Matheson, and T. P. D. Fan, "Thymidine phosphorylase induces angiogenesis in vivo and in vitro: an evaluation of possible mechanisms," *British Journal of Pharmacology*, vol. 139, pp. 219-231, 2003.
6. A. Moghaddam and R. Bicknell, "Expression of platelet-derived endothelial cell growth factor in *Escherichia coli* and confirmation of its thymidine phosphorylase activity," *Biochemistry*, vol. 31, pp. 12141-12146, 1992.
7. H. Oda, T. Hanami, T. Iwashita, M. Kojima, M. Itoh, and Y. Hayashizaki, "Synthesis of 5-acetyl-2-aminopyrrole C-deoxyribonucleoside," *Tetrahedron*, vol. 63, pp. 12747-12753, 2007.
8. M. Jalilian and M. Zahedi-Tabrizi, "Spectra and structure of binary azeotropes V-acetone-cyclopentane," *Spectrochimica Acta Part A: Molecular and Biomolecular Spectroscopy*, vol. 69, pp. 278-281, 2008.
9. M. Zupan, B. Stanovnik, and M. Tisler, "Heterocycles. XCVII. Pyridazines. LI. Synthetic approaches to pyridazino [2, 3-*a*]-1, 3, 5-triazines, a novel heterocyclic system," *The Journal of Organic Chemistry*, vol. 37, pp. 2960-2963, 1972.
10. W. Zeghida, J. Debray, S. Chierici, P. Dumy, and M. Demeunynck, "Concise synthesis of 2-amino-4 (3 H)-quinazolinones from simple (hetero) aromatic amines," *The Journal of Organic Chemistry*, vol. 73, pp. 2473-2475, 2008.
11. D. S. Dodd and Y. Zhao, "Solid-phase synthesis of N,N'-substituted acylguanidines," *Tetrahedron Letters*, vol. 42, pp. 1259-1262, 2001.
12. N. Primas, H. El-Kashef, J.-C. Lancelot, A. Lesnard, R. H. Dodd, and S. Raulta, "Triazine-fused β -carboline: a facile three-step, one-pot synthesis of novel 2-alkyl (aryl) amino and 2-dialkylamino-7*H*-[1,3,5] triazino [1',2':1,6] pyrido [3,4-*b*] indol-4-ones," *Arkivoc*, vol. 11, pp. 163-176, 2010.
13. A. Caruso, J.-C. Lancelot, H. El-Kashef, M. S. Sinicropi, R. Legay, A. Lesnard, et al., "A rapid and versatile synthesis of novel pyrimido [5, 4-*b*] carbazoles," *Tetrahedron*, vol. 65, pp. 10400-10405, 2009.
14. M. Kopp, J. C. Lancelot, S. Dagdag, H. Miel, and S. Rault, "A versatile synthesis of 2-amino-4*H*-pyrido [1,2-*a*][1,3,5] triazin-4-ones from 2-aminopyridines," *Journal of Heterocyclic Chemistry*, vol. 39, pp. 1061-1064, 2002.

15. Y. Hama, Y. Nobuhara, Y. Aso, T. Otsubo, and F. Ogura, "Preparation and properties of pyridine-analogue of TCNQ dianion salt," Bulletin of the Chemical Society of Japan, vol. 61, pp. 1683-1686, 1988.
16. J. Bergman and B. Pelcman, "Synthesis of carbazoles related to carbazomycin, hyellazole and ellipticine," Tetrahedron, vol. 44, pp. 5215-5228, 1988.

Cite this Article: Said Dagdag, Mounir Belbahloul, Mohamed Anouar, Maria Kopp, Abdellah Anouar, Mohamed Hmyene (2022). A Facile Three-Steps, One-Pot Synthesis of Novel 2-Alkylamino and 2-Dialkylamino-4H-Pyrido [1, 2-A][1,3,5] Triazin-4-Ones from 2-Aminopyridine and 2-Aminopicolines. International Journal of Current Science Research and Review, 5(4), 976-986